

ASSESSMENT OF SOCIO CULTURAL BELIEFS AND PRACTICES AMONG POST NATAL MOTHERS ABOUT HEALTH CARE IN GADAG DISTRICT KARNATAKA

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ABSTRACT

Background: Culture may be defined as a shared system of beliefs, values, and behavioural expectations that provide social structure for daily living. Much of the woman's behaviour during the postpartum period is strongly influenced by her cultural background, This study was conducted to identify the cultural practices among the postnatal mothers in selected PHC lakkundi village Gadag district. The data was collected from 200 samples. The postpartum period continues to be an important part of the tradition and culture among Indian women. But frequently the health of the postnatal women is neglected. So, the present study aimed to assess the factors influencing of cultural practices about the postnatal care and to identify the factors influencing the cultural beliefs and practices during the postnatal period among mothers and family members.

Objectives

- 1) To assess the factors influencing of cultural practices about the postnatal care.
- 2) To identify the factors influencing the cultural beliefs and practices during the postnatal period among mothers and family members.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted in rural village, Lakkundi that comes under Gadag district. Formal permission was obtained from Medical Officer of selected PHC. The data was obtained from 200 postnatal mother. The purpose of the study was explained to mothers and informed consent was obtained from them. Through purposive sampling, mothers were selected. Data was collected using a semi structured interview schedule. **Results:** Among the 200 women, over 75% of women had increased their diet intake postpartum. Vegetables such as brinjal and fruits like papaya were avoided by 58.5% and 63.6% women respectively. Among the mothers 80% consumed less than 500 ml of water every day and 22% did not drink milk at all. Many women didn't maintain personal hygiene. Many women took home remedies for faster recuperation. These practices were influenced by their mothers, ancestors, and the woman's educational status. **Conclusion:** Cultural beliefs about the postpartum practices are still popular among women in rural and slum areas. It is critical to identify the harmful practices and reinforce the positive healthy practices to make postpartum period a healthy and joyful period for the mother.

KEYWORDS: Cultural Beliefs; Practices; Antenatal Care; Postnatal Care; Socio-Cultural; Women.

INTRODUCTION

Postpartum period is a social as well as a personal event and has meaning well beyond the simple physiological events. It is marked by strong emotions, Postpartum period is a social as well as a personal event and has meaning well beyond the simple physiological events. It is marked by strong emotions, dramatic physical changes, new and altered relationships and the assumption of and adjustment to new role from the social status of woman to that of mother Culture is defined as a distinctive way of life of group of people.^[1,2,3,4] Postpartum care and diet varies, based on topography of the region, culture, tradition and religious practices

Culturally competent care involves knowledge of the various dimensions of care, including moving beyond the biomedical needs of the patient. Rather, a holistic approach is one that expands knowledge. Changes attitudes, and enhances clinical skills.^[5,6,7,8] This study was conducted to document the beliefs and practices along the prenatal, antenatal, through the peripartum period among women in Southern Ghana.^[9,10,11,12] It is critical to identify the harmful practices and reinforce the positive healthy practices to make postpartum period a healthy and joyful period for the mother. practices in rural India necessitated the conduct of the current research study, with the objective of assessing postnatal

beliefs and practices with respect to food taboos, personal hygiene, rest and confinement at Home.^[13,14,15,16] Feeding of colostrum, timing of initiation and duration of breastfeeding, umbilical cord care, and measures taken to prevent hypothermia of the newborn are important factors in health and survival during the neonatal period. In our community women receive information from family members, elders and traditional birth attendants. Hence, these groups, expectant mothers and mothers of newborns should be targeted with educational messages. Newborn care, similar to other human behaviors, is influenced by cultural beliefs. Hence exploration of cultural beliefs and practices of newborn care is essential.^[17&18] Culture is defined as passed down values, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors, including knowledge, art, traditions, customs, abilities, and similar skills and habits that human beings gain as a member of a society. Among the elements that shape the culture; morals, traditions, and customs are important¹⁻³. Societies' values, attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors affect individuals' lifestyles. Health and sickness are also concepts that fall within the cultural structure and differ according to culture⁴. Cultural differences can also be seen in the birth and postpartum periods, where some traditional practices are performed for the protection of the mother and baby.^[20,21,22,23,24]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design: A field based Cross-Sectional study.

Setting: Based on records and considering the frequency of delivery occurring in Gadag district Lakkundi PHC, a convenient sampling of 200 post-natal mothers were interviewed during the study period.

Estimation of sample size

Time series sampling technique

Total number of deliveries occurred in last 3 months
218(Aug, Sept, Oct 2022)

RESULTS

Table No 1: Distribution of Socio-demographic characteristics of participants (n=200)

Category	Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age groups	18-20 years	02	1
	21- 24 years	38	19
	25-28 years	124	62
	29-32 years	29	14.5
	33-36 years	01	0.5
	37-40 years	01	0.5
	<40 years	05	2.5
Educational status	Primary school	78	39
	High school	24	12
	PUC	05	2.5
	Degree & above	93	46.5
Religion	Hindu	40	20
	Muslim	51	25.5
	Christian	01	0.5
	OBC	83	41.5
	SC/ST	23	11.5

Availability of the mothers during data collection period
200

Participants: In this study we have included the postnatal mothers, newborn babies, caretaker, mother in law's. Data was obtained from those who given informed consent to participate in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Inclusion criteria were post- natal mothers delivered in Gadag district Lakkundi PHC.

Exclusion Criteria

- Post-natal mothers who are not willing to cooperate.
- Who are chronically ill

Source of data: Primary data was collected using pre tested semi structured questionnaire.

Sampling design: Purposive sampling technique.

Method of collection of data: Study was conducted for the Assessment of socio cultural beliefs and practices among postnatal mothers about health care in Gadag district Lakkundi PHC. The study was conducted using pre tested semi structured questionnaire by interacting with patients after taking informed written consent from the participants.

Data Analysis: The data collected entered into Microsoft excel and analyzed in terms of frequency and percentage and results are expressed in frequency and percentages.

Ethical Clearance: Ethical clearance obtained from IEC of KSRDPR University Gadag No: RDPRU/SEP/IEC/4/2021/9.

	Others	2	1
Occupation	Home maker	166	83
	Laborer	02	1
	Business	12	6
	Others	20	10
Socio economic status	APL	102	51
	BPL	98	49
Type of family	Joint	63	31.5
	Nuclear	137	68.5

Total 200 members participated in the study, almost half of the participants are of the age group of 25 -28 years, quarter of them are 21-24 years, less than quarter of them are 29 -32 years, Among 200 participants 4 are got 2nd marriage. Most of participants are literate. Nearly half of

the study participants are home maker and nearly quarter of them are doing working in their own shops, farm labours. Almost all of them of study participants belong to above poverty level (APL) income families. Half of the participants belong to Nuclear.

Table No 2: Distribution of cultural beliefs and Practices existed among study participants (n=200).

Variables		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1. Drinking more water will increase cooling of body	Agree	185	92.5
	Disagree	15	7.5
2. Metal and broom stick will prevent evil spirit	Agree	139	69.5
	Disagree	61	30.5
3. Eating dried ginger is good for postpartum bleeding because	Controls postpartum bleeding	177	88.5
	Uterine cleansing agent	23	11.5

Table No 2.1: Distribution of cultural beliefs and Practice existed among study participants (n=200).

Variables	Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1. Giving bath everyday	Yes	185	92.5
	No	15	7.5
2. Reason for umbilical cord is buried	It is done since old days	150	75
	It is formality	45	22.5
	Because baby will become thief in future	05	2.5

Cultural beliefs among postnatal mother and child. It was observed that a large majority of study participants not drinking water because it increases cooling of body. As

far as cultural beliefs related to new born child one of the major cultural beliefs among study participants is burying the umbilical cord.

Table No 3: Distribution of the cultural practices among study participants.

Variables	Responses	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1. Consuming hot food after delivery	Yes	192	96
	No	08	4
2. Regular hot bath for 40 days.	Yes	190	95
	No	10	5
3. Sambrani droop to episiotomy wound	Yes	104	52
	No	86	43

Table No 3.1: Distribution of Beliefs and practices existed among study participants for protection.

Variables	Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Application of Kajal on Eyebrow and Cheek and tieng black thread on hand and neck.	For purification ceremony	144	72
	Prevent bad eye	56	28

The cultural practices among postnatal mother and child. It was observed that a large majority of study participants consuming hot food compulsory Quarter of postnatal

mother take sambarani dhoop to episiotomy wound. Majority of mothers used to apply kajal and black thread to child for purification ceremony.

Table No 4: Factors Influencing the PNC about cultural beliefs and Practices.

Factors	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Ancestors	07	3.5
Aunt	18	9
Mother in law	14	7
Mother	161	80.5

Factors influencing postnatal care about cultural beliefs and practices Majority of them are mother quarter of are influenced by there aunt and few are influenced by there mother in law few are influenced by there ancestors.

DISCUSSION

Study population

In the study majority of postnatal mothers belongs to age group of 25 -28 years completed their secondary level education at Lakkundi village Gadag district. The similar findings in Tirupati, (1) Mangalore, (2)Turkey (6), Kurnool (4).

Cultural beliefs

In the current study almost all (96%) postnatal mothers replied that follow all cultural beliefs. In this study majority of participants used to bury baby's umbilical cord (75%) A study conducted at Nepal^[10] 80% Bangladesh^[7] 70% found the similar opinion.

A large majority of study participants not drinking water because it increases cooling of body(85%) A study same conducted in southern Ghana 75% has also has same opinion.

Cultural practices

In this study majority 72% of apply kajal to baby's face to prevent evil eye A study conducted in Mangalore 85% have similar opinion. Majority of study participants consuming hot food compulsory and Half of postnatal mother take sambarani dhoop to episiotomy wound 77%. Because it stop postnatal Heamorrhage, A study conducted at south India 66%(8), Indonesia70%(9) found similar opinion.

Influencing the PNC about cultural beliefs and Practices

In the present study majority of postnatal mothers influenced by their mother, and also their mother used to give regular bath to baby, In our study majority of postnatal mothers influenced by their mother, and also their mother used to give regular bath to baby.^[26,27,28,29]

CONCLUSION

Cultural beliefs and postpartum practices are still popular among women in rural and slum areas in Lakkundi village. It is critical to identify the harmful practices and reinforce the positive, healthy practices to make the postpartum period a healthy and joyful period for the mother. In the study region, people must first determine which practices are dangerous and which are harmless in order to navigate motherhood. While practices such as

regularly washing oneself helped to maintain hygiene, solitude at home and avoiding visitors might lower the likelihood of both the mother and the infant catching illnesses.

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